

Innovative Multidisciplinary Research

The Influence of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, ROA (Return On Asset), and Net Profit/Loss on GWM (Minimum Reserve Requirement) with Firm Size as a Moderation Variable in Islamic Banking in Indonesia Period of 2018-2023

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine the influence of ZISWAF, ROA, and Current Year Net Profit/Loss on GWM using Company Size as a Moderate Variable. This research aims to provide an understanding of Primary Variables-Hub Variables, identify the influence of company size, provide management practice guidance, and contribute to academic knowledge. The sample used in this research consists of financial sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) in 2018. First quarter of 2023.Q3. Purposive sampling is the sampling technique used, with a total sample of five Islamic banks over a period of six years. The data analysis techniques used include Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) with the Eviews 12 application and Regression Analysis Panel Data. The findings of this study confirm ZISWAF payments, and laboratory results sufficiently demonstrate the study's impact on GWM, while wadiah giro savings show an insignificant impact on GWM for 2018 Q1 to 2023 Q3. Furthermore, it is known that the variables ZISWAF, ROA, and profit and loss have a significant and simultaneous effect on GWM. It is hoped that further research will increase the number of independent variables that will be studied so that other variables can be identified that have an impact on the Mandatory Minimum Reserve (GWM) of Indonesian banking.

Keywords: ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, ROA, GWM net profit and loss, firm size.

A. INTRODUCTION

In general, banks that adhere to Islamic law can be defined as financial institutions that provide banking services for small businesses such as loan disbursement, credit card payments and installment loans. According to the teachings contained in the Al-Qur'an and Hadith, banks that operate in accordance with sharia banking principles are called sharia banks. Therefore, Islamic banks must be able to monitor policies that contain democratic principles and other matters that conflict with Islamic law. The differences between Islamic and conventional banks may be caused by several different factors. First and foremost, banks that adhere to Islamic law do not use an interest system in their operations; conventional banks do. This has very strong implications which have a negative impact on the quality of operations and products handled by Islamic banks (Agustin, 2021).

In general, ZISWAF has three main pillars: financial support, grants, and loans. The storage of collected ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds is all collection activities, such as socialization/marketing and collecting ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds from muzakki and wakif. ZISWAF for mustahik and

mauquf'alaih is entitled with various programs in the social sector, namely social humanitarian, educational, health, da'wah and economic programs. More specifically, as a major initiative to integrate zakat and waqf which are components of Islamic law, the distribution of funds can be used to strengthen the halal industry in particular. However, peer-to-peer lending activities include monitoring, evaluation and HR, finance and planning activities. In contrast, the main ecosystems that negatively impact the value chain in the ZISWAF sector consist of the following: demand-side perspective (mass society), regulatory and collective perspective, technological perspective, research and development, and research and development (Lubis & Latifah, 2019) .

Profitability is measured using Return On Assets (ROA) to see how well a business is able to generate income and manage investments. ROA to compare the amount of assets after tax with the amount between laboratories. The more ROA means the better the company's ability to handle risks and manage investments. Increase ROA to increase the company's ability to handle losses. According to substitution theory, increasing firm value depends on the firm's ability to disclose financial information, which includes currency exchange operations and strategies for generating profits. If a business provides good information about ROA, investors will be more positive about the information provided. This signal has the potential to increase investor confidence in making investments which will then have a negative impact on the company's performance (Putri & Utomo, 2021) .

Minimum Statutory Reserves are related to bank liquidity which is visible in bank operations, especially in the areas of credit and liabilities; In addition, the new understanding of the Statutory Reserve is related to utilitarian theory and provides benefits for the banking system, especially in the area of liquidity needs. However, this new development also has a negative impact, because interbank loans with a high Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) are increasingly difficult to obtain because banks in Indonesia have to provide loans. This is the reason why banks that previously accepted giro payments for implementing the Minimum Wage provisions are now obliged to increase the Minimum Wage provisions at Bank Indonesia by at least five percent.

GWM is one of the monetary policy instruments used by the Central Bank. By increasing the reserve requirement ratio, this will cause a change in the amount of currency that can be traded through changes in exchange rates. Setting a minimum requirement will reduce the amount of money distributed compared to the amount of money already deposited and will act as a buffer against the total amount of money. Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) is a currency exchange rate adjustment tool because it has the ability to reduce exchange rate volatility. This instrument is used as a tool to stabilize the overall amount of money in circulation. Therefore, this sentiment must be in harmony with the national economy. Since its inception in the early years of the 15th century until now, Bank Indonesia has undergone several changes in order to set GWM standards that must be adhered to by Indonesian banks. This is done so that the liquidity of the Indonesian banking system is more stable and resistant to crises (Shafiin, 2023) .

Company size has a negative contribution to moderating financial leverage, with a coefficient of determination of 1.76 and a significant value of 0.0068 <0.05. This is because the debt user himself has two dampers that are permanently open. Although hedge funds provide tax protection and influence stock prices through diversifying investment strategies, hedge funds with higher betas can lead to negative exchange rate conditions because the returns of invested funds are consistently higher than their costs. In the

context of this study, companies with large sample sizes and significant capital requirements will likely require large-scale debt sampling, which may be detrimental to the company if ignored. This is also in accordance with research which states that a company's leverage creates an inverted U shape. On the other hand, the influence of company size on the influence of asset management on company value makes a positive contribution of 0.43 with a significance level of $0.0216 < 0.05$. It can be concluded that business size itself has a positive impact in strengthening the relationship between asset management and company value. Through productive and ideal asset allocation, not only sales and profits can be generated, but new ideas can also be generated (Amelinda et al., 2023) .

The aim of this research is to determine the influence of ZISWAF, ROA, and Net Profit/Loss for the Year on GWM using Company Size as a Moderate Variable. This research aims to provide an understanding of Primary Variables-Hub Variables, identify the influence of company size, provide management practice guidance, and contribute to academic knowledge.

B. LITERATURE STUDY

ZISWAF

Zizwaf is a tool for allocating resources in the Islamic economic system, and the collection of zakat is a mandatory instrument. Therefore, the other three tools serve as guides in doing business with humans. Zakat is useful for poor people to open up employment opportunities as well as capital. In order to have a stable income and be able to support his family safely, this is done in accordance with the aim of zakat, namely equal distribution of income. Zakat distribution is used not only for distribution purposes but also to stabilize economic activities. Therefore, Allah SWT ordered them to remember to pay zakat, infaq and alms (Hakim et al., 2023) .

ROA

Return On Assets (ROA) is a ratio that shows the rate of return (rush) relative to the number of active employees in a company. In addition, ROA provides a measure of managerial effectiveness in terms of investment allocation. According to Dan Hery (2014), return on assets (ROA) is a ratio that shows several significant asset contributions in creating a stable business. In other words, this ratio is used to reduce the amount of significant savings that will result from each rupiah of funds included in overall assets. The higher the ROA, the higher the level of profit obtained by the company and the more profitable the company's position in terms of asset utilization (Wijaya, 2019) .

PROFIT AND LOSS

Zaki Baridwan (2000:31) states that "Profit (Profit) is the value that arises from transactions that may occur in a business, as well as from other transactions or events that have a negative impact on overall business performance over a period of time certain. unless it is the result of employee income or investment." "The value of equity (profit) comes from the results or investment of the owner and not the main activity (entity) of transactions or other events that affect the entity during a certain period," said Sofyan Syahfri Harahap (2001: 115). Based on several studies, it can be concluded that profit is more closely related to profits and losses that occur at key or peak times in an organization academic year after the tax debt test was corrected." Only around fifty

percent of the current book profit was used as a particular operating mode for the bank or business entity to experience losses throughout the study year, all of these losses were detrimental to the current operating method (Hapsari & Saputra, 2018) .

GWM

Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) is the amount of money that every depositor must report to Bank Indonesia for every unit of money generated. GWM is very dependent on the interest rate (GWM Ratio) set by Bank Indonesia. The higher GWM ratio reported by Bank Indonesia is in line with a period of smaller credit expansion for Commercial Banks. However, GWM will limit bank credit expansion days, which means it will reduce bank credit expansion capabilities. The best course of action for banks is to follow the above rules; However, this must be ensured so that the GWM does not continue to reduce Bank Indonesia's policy and the money obtained ineffectively becomes smaller. In the event that the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) of a Commercial Bank exceeds the upper GWM limit (5%) set by Bank Indonesia, the stricter limit known as the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) will be reduced. To meet the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) of at least 5%, BI will provide a demand deposit bonus of around 3% every year. Thus, the implementation of the Mandatory Minimum Reserve (GWM) at Bank Indonesia will increase the size of bank branches which will ultimately increase profitability. (Iriani, 2013) .

FIRM SIZE

Company Size, also known as Company size, refers to the size, whether large or small, of a particular company. "Company size is the size of a company," said Andi Kartika (2011: 161). On the other hand, Hery (2017:12) states that: "Business expansion shows the size of a company which can be expressed as total assets or as total sales revenue." The more assets or overall purchase price, the larger the size of a business (Meriam, 2019) .

The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM)

The influence of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds Fund Receipts on GWM at each bank depends on the policies and strategies of each bank. Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds can have an impact on bank operations related to lending and deposit activities, so that it can impact investor results. However, acceptance or rejection of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds related to GWM depends on bank policy. Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds is effective for the ratio added in the contract cooperation business (Islamic and Islamic), which has been added by the investor customer. In addition, the ZISWAF withdrawal policy can have an impact on the capital adequacy ratio (CAR) and Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) in Islamic banks. ZISWAF withdrawals can have an impact on investment activities and other withdrawals, which can then impact investors' results, but only indirectly or not at all on GWM (Sahli & Evan, 2020) .

The Effect of Return On Assets (ROA) on the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM)

The effect of the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) on the bank's Return on Assets (ROA) is negative. This means that the greater the GWM, the ROA decreases. This

is due to non-productive bank fees that need to be paid to find out the actual amount of bank fees. The minimum demand deposit requirement is imposed by the central bank (Bank Indonesia) and is based on the number of demand deposits transferred by the bank to BI. If there is a problem with bank liquidity, the bank can communicate with BI secretly. However, provisions regarding GWM often make it difficult for banks because they force banks to save and invest their funds in the form of demand deposits at BI so that they are active but not effective in generating primary GWM, which is 5% of primary GWM. Third Party Deposits. As a result of these non-productive funds, bank costs will increase, which unfortunately will reduce bank income. According to research conducted by Mabruroh (2004) and Husnah (2006), the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) has a positive effect on ROA. However, the results of research conducted by Triono (2007) showed that GWM had a negative impact on laboratory changes over two years. This shows that the cost of funds will reduce bank income. Based on the information provided, it can be concluded that the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) has a negative impact on the Return on Assets (ROA) of a bank, which is caused by the existence of non-productive debt which must be repaid to the bank to determine the amount of the debt (Nuzulia, 1967)

Effect of Net Profit and Loss on Minimum Statutory Reserves (GWM)

Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) is influenced by Net Profit and Loss (LRB) because it impacts Return on Assets (ROA). The larger the LRB will result in lower GWM, which will increase ROA. This is due to non-productive bank fees that need to be paid to find out the actual amount of bank fees. However, provisions regarding GWM often make it difficult for banks because they force banks to save and invest their funds in the form of demand deposits at BI so that they are active but not effective in generating primary GWM, which is 5% of primary GWM. Third Party Deposits. As a result of these non-productive funds, bank costs will increase, which unfortunately will reduce bank profits (Iriani, 2013) .

The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) in Firm Size Moderation

Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds can have an impact on bank operations related to lending and deposit activities, so that it can impact investor results. Banks have the ability to support the goal of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) which is to improve the economy of the entire population as a whole. Apart from that, banks are able to optimize investment and consumption allocated to potential business sectors such as trade, rental, property and real estate, as well as consumer goods (Avila & Esperanza, 2022) .

The Effect of Return on Assets (ROA) on the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) in Firm Size Moderation

Firm size is a scale on which the largest firm sizes can be classified using the log of stock market size, active totals, and means. Based on the graph above, the size of a business can be classified into three categories: large businesses, small businesses, and startups. The size of this company is determined by its total assets. One of the main tools for reducing the size of a business is expansion. Some common metrics for determining the size of a business include employees, activity, sales, market value, and value added.

Based on the analysis above, it can be concluded that profitability is the ability of a business to generate income that is not affected by fluctuating profits due to costs incurred to maximize profits. The statistic Return On Assets (ROA) is the term used in this research. The profitability ratio, which compares the bank's total assets with laboratory assets before payment, shows the level of efficiency in selling assets carried out by a bank that is financially healthy. Based on the statistics above, it can be concluded that the working hours usually used by banks are profitable working hours. For the business world, especially banking, profitability is usually an important factor that needs to be considered because low profitability indicates that a business is not operating efficiently. The first efficiency can be understood by comparing lab results with the capital or wealth used to produce lab results, or in other words, by reducing profitability. The meaning of profitability can be understood to the point where a bank's ability to provide profitable results comes from its operational and non-operational results. In banking, profitability is also one of the factors that determines whether a bank is healthy or not, apart from capital, active quality, management and liquidity (Andri et al., 2015) .

The Effect of Net Profit and Loss on Minimum Statutory Reserves (GWM) in Firm Size Moderation

(Company Size) is the largest size of a company which can be categorized in several ways, including total assets, total workforce, and total revenue. The size of a company compared to its total assets is a measure of the size of the company. from the company; The greater the total assets owned by a company, the greater the company itself. Business expansion has a significant impact on laboratory quality because large companies can produce quality laboratories so that they can increase the finances of the company's workforce. Seven studies were conducted under the title "Impact on Business Performance, Profitability, Leverage, Material Equity, and Institutional Equity in Relation to Laboratory Quality." States that leverage and profitability have a significant negative impact on laboratory quality. This research was conducted with the title "Evolution of Profitability, Growth, Leverage, Operating Cycle, and Prudence on Profit Quality Using Company Size as a Moderate Variable." stated that growth, operational cycles, and prudence have no effect on laboratory quality. The research was conducted using the terms Leverage, Liquidity, and Company Size as moderating variables for lab quality. States that leverage and liquidity have a negative impact on laboratory quality. Writing with the title "The Influence of Profitability, Growth, Leverage, Operational Cycle and Prudence on Profit Quality with Company Size as a Moderating Variable", the author continues his research (Gultom, 2021) .

The Influence of ZISWAF Fund Receipts, ROA, and Profit and Loss on GWM in Firm Size Moderation

The following is the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable:

C. RESEARCH METHODS

Methods include the type of method or type of skill used, data collection procedures, and data analysis techniques. Explains in a straightforward manner the scientific method for searching and obtaining data and is related to the methodology and technical process of conducting research which is described in straightforward, simple and direct language, not theoretical but through practical application. The purpose of this research is to determine the effect of ZISWAF, ROA, and profit and loss on GWM by using Company Size as a Moderation variable for the 2015 Period.Q1. December 2023.Q3. It is hoped that this research can clarify how the amount of money generated is used to find out how Murabahah Receivables are affected, as well as how company size influences the amount of money generated. The data analysis method used in this research includes Moderated Regression Analysis. (MRA) and Panel Data Regression Models. Interaction analysis, also known as moderated regression analysis (MRA), uses analytical techniques that strengthen the integrity of the sample and provide a basis for providing the influence of moderator variables (Rokhlinasari & Hidayat, 2016) .

The following is the model equation in panel data regression analysis:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e_i$$

Where:

Y = GWM

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X1 = Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

X2 = ROA Fund Receipt

X3 = Net Profit/Loss for the current year

e_i = Error

Hypothesis testing in this study uses regression analysis with the moderating variable Moderating Regression Analysis (MRA), the regression equation contains elements of interaction with the following equation formula:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 Z + \beta_5 X_1 * Z + \beta_6 X_2 * Z + \beta_7 X_3 * Z + e_i$$

Where:

Y = GWM

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X1 = Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

X2 = ROA Fund Receipt

X3 = Net Profit/Loss for the current year

Z = Firm Size

X1*Z = Interaction of the influence of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds with moderation of firm size

X2*Z = Interaction of the influence of ROA fund receipt with firm size moderation

X3*Z = Interaction of the Effect of Danalaba Receipts/Clean Losses for the Mobile Year with Firm Size Moderation

e_i = Error.

D. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

	X1	X2	X3	Y	Z
Mean	25082.01	0.835426	262898.8	5.261391	16.65089
Median	18.00000	0.430000	22354.00	5.090000	16.50847
Maximum	669879.0	4.080000	4260182.	11.90000	19.58335
Minimum	0.000000	-6.720000	-818324.0	0.000000	14.11809
Std. Dev.	87500.44	1.182268	785721.2	1.938077	1.474195
Observations	115	115	115	115	115

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Based on Table 1, the number of financial sector research samples is 115 available on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) for the 2018 Q1-2023.Q3 fiscal year. Based on the descriptive statistics results in Table 1, it can be concluded that the ZISWAF Fund Receipts variable (X1) has the following values: maximum 669879.0, minimum 0.000000, median 18.00000, average 25082.01, and standard deviation 87500.44.

Based on the results of descriptive statistics in Table 4.1, it can be concluded that the ROA variable produced using the debt to equity ratio has a negative value. as follows: the average is 0.835426, the median is 0.430000, the maximum is 4.080000, the minimum is -6.720000, and the standard deviation is 1.182268.

Based on the results of descriptive statistics in Table 4.1, it can be concluded that Profit and Loss (X3) used with the Debt to Equity Ratio formula has the following values: average 262898.8, median 22354.00, maximum 4260182, minimum -818324.0, and standard deviation 785721.2.

Based on the results of descriptive statistics in Table 4.1, it can be concluded that GWM which is based on Return on Assets and is subject to variation has the following values: average 5.261391, median 5.090000, maximum 11.90000, minimum 0.000000, and

standard deviation 1.938077.

Based on the descriptive statistics results in Table 4.1, it can be concluded that Company Size with a hit rate of 16.65089, a median of 16.50847, a maximum of 19.58335, a minimum of 14.11809, and a standard deviation of 1.474195 is the level variable hit value for Tobins' Q.

Selection of Panel Data Regression Models

The use of regression models on panel data is an analytical technique to determine the best combination of fixed, random or general effects.

Test Chow

This experiment was carried out to determine the most appropriate model between the Common Effect Model (CEM) and the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Table 2. Chow Test Results

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.163115	(4,106)	0.3313
Cross-section Chi-square	4.939849	4	0.2935

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Based on Table 2, the results of the Chow test show that the cross-sectional chi-square probability is around $0.2935 > 0.05$. Thus it can be said that in this research the most appropriate model to use is the Common Effect Model (CEM).

LM Test

Table 3. LM Test Results

	Test Hypothesis		
	Cross-section	Time	Both
Breusch-Pagan	0.540054 (0.4624)	61.19460 (0.0000)	61.73466 (0.0000)

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

It can be seen from table 4 above that the LM test results show a significance level of $0.4624 > 0.05$. Thus, it can be stated that in this example the best model to use is CEM.

CLASSIC ASSUMPTION TEST

Normality Test

The normality test is used to determine whether there are errors in a regression that has a normal distribution. If the number of errors is mostly smaller than the average number then it is said to be normally distributed. Formal residual normality assessment can be determined using the following methodology, developed by Jarque-Bera using the

following hypothesis: $H_0: \epsilon_i$ equals 0 with normally distributed data errors. H_1 : Data errors do not follow a normal distribution, and ϵ_i does not equal 0. Recap: Eviews 12 (information provided by the author).

Based on the output above, the Jarque Bera Test probability value is $0.736150 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the data in this study is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Multilinearity analysis is used to determine whether there is a significant correlation between the dependent and independent variables in a regression model. A good regression model must guarantee the absence of skewness between dependent variables. If a correlated variable is independent, then the correlated variable is not orthogonal (the correlation value is different from zero).

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test Results

	X1	X2	X3
X1	1.000000	0.259673	0.760587
X2	0.259673	1.000000	0.394268
X3	0.760587	0.394268	1.000000

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Based on Table 5, the results of multilinear regression analysis can be shown if the correspondence coefficient for all independent variables is less than 0.85. This shows that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the research data.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity occurs when the model being viewed does not have consistent variations across observations. White noise is generated by regressing all independent variables into squared errors.

Table 6. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-1.844534	1.483336	-1.243503	0.2163
X1	-1.10E-06	1.96E-06	-0.561978	0.5753
X2	0.049694	0.100686	0.493549	0.6226
X3	-2.69E-08	2.34E-07	-0.114762	0.9088

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test, it can be seen that the calculated probability is less than or equal to 0.06 for X1, X3, and less than or equal to 0.05 for X2. Each regression model is considered free from heteroscedasticity if the probability density is less than 0.05. Thus, from the regression model used in this research it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity occurs in the variable X2.

Panel Data Regression Analysis

In this section, panel data regression analysis is presented using the best model, namely the Fixed Effect Model.

Table 7. Panel Data Regression Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.620777	2.274389	1.591978	0.1143
X1	-2.06E-06	3.00E-06	-0.686716	0.4937
X2	0.648158	0.154381	4.198422	0.0001
X3	2.29E-07	3.59E-07	0.638072	0.5248
Z	0.065504	0.138210	0.473946	0.6365

Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)

One way to think of moderating variables is that they can strengthen or balance the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The following are the results of the test analysis.

Table 8. Moderation Regression Analysis Test

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.826271	3.276624	0.252171	0.8014
X1	-0.000620	0.000458	-1.353587	0.1787
X2	3.897501	3.664094	1.063701	0.2899
X3	5.90E-06	2.56E-05	0.230696	0.8180
Z	0.242779	0.200453	1.211152	0.2285
X1Z	3.20E-05	2.37E-05	1.349293	0.1801
X2Z	-0.198537	0.219353	-0.905101	0.3674
X3Z	-3.04E-07	1.32E-06	-0.230735	0.8180

Statistical Test

T test

To determine whether a correlated variable has a statistically significant influence on the

dependent variable, use the t test. Additionally, it is used to understand how each independent variable influences each dependent variable, using significance levels of 0.05 and 5% for each variable to ensure accuracy and consistency.

Table	9	T		Test		Results
		Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	
		C	0.826271	3.276624	0.252171	0.8014
		X1	-0.000620	0.000458	-1.353587	0.1787
		X2	3.897501	3.664094	1.063701	0.2899
		X3	5.90E-06	2.56E-05	0.230696	0.8180
		Z	0.242779	0.200453	1.211152	0.2285
		X1Z	3.20E-05	2.37E-05	1.349293	0.1801
		X2Z	-0.198537	0.219353	-0.905101	0.3674
		X3Z	-3.04E-07	1.32E-06	-0.230735	0.8180

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Based on the partial t test that was completed during this research, it can be concluded that the t test results obtained were as follows:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds is effective in GWM. 0.000620 as the coefficient of determination and 0.1787 as the probability which indicates a value higher than the 0.5 or 5% significance level. This shows that the receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds did not have a negative impact on GWM in the business sector during 2018Q1-2023.Q3.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): ROA has advantages over GWM. With a coefficient of determination of 3.897501 and a probability of 0.2899, it is greater than the significance level of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that ROA has no effect on GWM in businesses operating in the financial sector during Q12023.Q3.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): GWM income Profit and Loss. With a coefficient of determination of 5.90E-06 and a probability coefficient of 0.8180, it is greater than the significance level of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that the impact of Profit and Loss on the GWM of the financial industry in the period 2018Q1-2023 is zero.Q3.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Company size has a negative effect on GWM in ZISWAF Revenue Funds. It has a coefficient of determination of 3.20E-05 and a probability coefficient of 0.1801, more than the significance level of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that company size cannot mitigate the impact of ZISWAF dividend payments on GWM in the real estate sector throughout the Q1-Q3 2018-2023 period.

Hypothesis 5 (H5): ROA is moderated by Firm Size in GWM. With a coefficient of determination of -0.198537 and a probability coefficient of 0.3674, it is less significant than 0.5 or 5%. This shows that company size has the ability to moderate ROA relative to GWM for businesses operating in the financial sector during Q12023.Q3.

Hypothesis 6 (H6): Net profit and loss is moderated by Firm Size in GWM. With a coefficient of determination of -3.04E-07 and a probability coefficient of 0.8180, less than 5% or 0.5. This shows that larger company size can moderate net profit and loss against GWM in the financial sector more effectively for businesses operating in 2018Q1-2023.Q3.

F test

The F test is used to determine whether an independent variable simultaneously has a statistically significant influence on the dependent variable.

Table 10 F Test Results

0.671068	Prob(F-statistic)	0.000194
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Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

In the current research, the F test uses a significance threshold of 0.05 or 5% with criteria stating that if the F threshold is slightly less than 0.05 then the regression coefficient can be used. The F test results in Table 11 above show that the F significance is 0.000001, which is smaller than the significance of 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that ZISWAF Fund Receipts, ROA, and Ziswaf Fund Receipts individually have a negative impact on GWM.

Coefficient of Determination Test

The coefficient of determination is used to highlight the significant contribution of certain independent variables in the regression model while explaining variations in the dependent variable.

Table 11 Determination Coefficient Test Results

Adjusted R-squared	0.150550
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Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Based on Table 12, the results of the GWM regression analysis as the dependent variable can be used to calculate Adjusted R² of 0.150550. This shows that around 15.05% of the GWM variable can be explained by ZISWAF, ROA and Net Profit and Loss. Instead, this can be explained by other independent variables in the model. On the other hand, around 84.95% can be explained by other variables in the regression model.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM)

Based on Table 9, research findings show that the probability of receiving a ZISWAF deposit is 0.1787, less than 0.05. The test results also show a negative trend with a coefficient of -0.000620 and a t-statistic of -1.353587. Thus, it can be concluded that the receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds has a negative impact on GWM. Thus, the hypothesis tested by researchers is H1: the effect of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on GWM remission. The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Qonita (2020). Based on previous research

findings, it can be concluded that recipients of ZISWAF loans can increase the amount of bank savings which will have a negative impact on GWM. If total bank deposits increase, the GWM will also increase.

The Effect of ROA on the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM)

Based on Table 9, the research results show that the ROA probability of 0.2899 is higher than 0.05. The test results also show a positive trend with a coefficient of 3.897501 and a t-statistic of 1.063701. Therefore, it can be concluded that ROA has no effect on GWM. Thus, the hypothesis put forward by the researcher is H2: ROA has a negative effect on GWM.

The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Nurul Hidayatul M et al. (2023). Based on research findings, it can be concluded that increasing bank demand deposits can increase overall demand deposits, thereby increasing the GWM. However, savings deposits can also have a negative impact on a bank's return on equity (ROE). Return on equity (ROE) is an indicator of a company's ability to manage its capital based on banks.

Effect of Net Profit and Loss on Minimum Statutory Reserves (GWM)

Based on Table 9, the research results show that the probability of profit and loss is approximately equal to 0.8180, which is less than 0.05. The test results also show a negative trend with a coefficient of 5.90E-06 and a t-statistic of 0.230696. Therefore, it can be concluded that ROA has an influence on GWM. Thus, the hypothesis proposed by researchers is H3: lab losses have a significant effect on the measured GWM.

The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Augustina et al. (2021). Based on research findings, it can be concluded that higher low-cost income can increase the amount of bank deposits, thereby increasing the GWM. This can improve the bank's market position and help reduce the risk of losses.

Firm Size Moderates the Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on GWM

Based on Table 9, the research results show that the probability of interaction between ZISWAF and company size is 0.1801 which is less than 0.05. The test results also show a positive trend with a coefficient of 3.20E-05 and a t-statistic of 1.349293. These results indicate that profitability can mitigate the negative impact between ZISWAF and GWM. Thus, the hypothesis tested by researchers is H4: Company size mediates the effect of ZISWAF withdrawal on the occurrence of GWM.

The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Rusmini & Aji (2019). Based on research findings, business size is a factor that can influence the impact of cuts in Zakat, Infaq, Alms and Waqf (ZISWAF) on Gross World Product (GWP) or Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Even though GWP and GDP do not have a linear correlation with GWM, the monetary relationship between GWP and GDP can have a significant impact on GWM.

Firm Size Moderates the Effect of ROA on GWM

Based on Table 9, research findings show that the probability of interaction between ROA and company size is around 0.3674, more than 0.05. The test results also show a negative trend with a coefficient of -0.198537 and a t-statistic of -0.905101. These results

indicate that profitability cannot fully account for the difference in ROA and GWM. Thus, the hypothesis that researchers test is H5: Company size modifies the impact of ROA on GWM.

The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Rohmalyani & Mais (2020). Based on research findings, it can be concluded that the influence of company size on wadiah savings deposits is complex and depends on several factors. In general, a larger business can increase ROA because it has more customers, is more effective at work, has more employees, is more capable in its field, has better efficiency, performance, marketing capabilities, management policies, is more equitable, has more a lot of equity, and have a larger customer base. However, larger businesses may also have stricter operational and expense policies, which can reduce labor costs.

Firm Size Moderates the Effect of Profit and Loss on GWM

Based on Table 9, the research findings show that the interaction probability between laboratory and company size is around 0.8180, which is less than 0.05. The test results also show a positive trend with a coefficient of $-3.04E-07$ and a t-statistic of -0.230735 . The research results show that profitability can significantly reduce the difference between profit and loss and GWM. Thus, the hypothesis that researchers test is H6: Company size modifies the effect of net profit on the GWM received.

The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Navita et al. (2023). Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the influence of firm size on net profit and loss is a moderator. Firm size can influence net profit and loss in various ways, such as efficiency, performance, marketing capabilities, management policies, suitability, and measuring company size.

Effect of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, ROA, Simultaneous Net Profit and Loss on GWM

Based on the data in Table 10, it can be concluded that the ZISWAF, ROA and profit and loss variables have a significant effect on GWM. This is caused by the significance threshold being less than $0.000194 < 0.05$. Research findings show that the amount received from ZISWAF, ROA, and profit and loss have a significant and simultaneous influence on GWM. Thus, the hypothesis proposed by the researcher is H7: receipt of funds from ZISWAF, ROA, and lab fees paid correctly.

The coefficient of determination, also called R Square, produces a value of 0.150550. Interpretation of the graph shows that the contribution of the independent variable to changes in value is around 15.05%, while the remaining 84.95% is influenced by other factors. Therefore, more independent variables can be used to conduct further research.

E. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the T test (Partial) of this research, it can be concluded that the receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds and profit and loss show a significant negative influence on GWM. This means that if the amount of ZISWAF and the resulting net profit loss is higher, the GWM will decrease, and vice versa. ROA shows a negligible influence on GWM. This means that if ROA is high, GWM will also increase, but not by much.

Meanwhile, for the F test (Simultaneous), it was found that the variables ZISWAF fund receipts, ROA, and net profit and loss had a simultaneous effect on GWM. This means

that when these three variables are taken together and analyzed, there is a less significant impact on the reserve requirement. This shows that there is a correlation or relationship between the combination of these variables and the level of financing in Islamic banking. In the R² (Coefficient of Determination) test results, it was found that all independent variables (ZISWAF fund receipts, ROA, and net profit and loss) were unable or did not have a strong relationship to explain variations in GWM. All independent variables (ZISWAF fund receipts, ROA, and net profit and loss) are only able to explain variations in GWM of 22.9%. This can be interpreted as meaning that changes in the independent variable tend to be uncorrelated or unrelated to changes that occur in the dependent variable.

This research has several limitations, namely the observation period in this study is only between 2018 and 2023 with quarterly data, so it does not show a significant trend for each variable. As well as the use of variables which are limited to 5 variables, including ZISWAF fund receipts, ROA, net profit and loss, GWM and Firm Size.

In future research, it is hoped that the number of independent variables that will be studied will be increased, so that other variables can be identified that influence the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) of sharia banks in Indonesia. It is also recommended to increase the number of research objects in the form of other sharia share companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI).

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